

Reduction of Power Quality Perturbations: A Review

Gerard N. Obiora ✉

Department of Electrical/Electronics & Telecommunication Engineering, College of Engineering, Bells University of Technology, Ota, Nigeria

Festus O. Oghenegweke ✉

Department of Electrical/Electronics & Telecommunication Engineering, College of Engineering, Bells University of Technology, Ota, Nigeria

Godwin O. Igbinosa ✉

Department of Electrical/Electronics & Telecommunication Engineering, College of Engineering, Bells University of Technology, Ota, Nigeria

Tobenna Obidire ✉

Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Nigeria

Collins B. Fiemobebefa ✉

Department of Electrical/Electronics & Telecommunication Engineering, College of Engineering, Bells University of Technology, Ota, Nigeria

Oluwaseun A. Bamido ✉

Department of Electrical/Electronics & Telecommunication Engineering, College of Engineering, Bells University of Technology, Ota, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT:

Power is usually generated by various power plants and transmitted at high voltages to the end users. This is made possible through a sophisticated network of diverse components utilized in a given power system. Also, every day, domestic and commercial activities such as cooking, transportation, manufacturing, illumination of offices and homes, air conditioning, refrigeration, and the likes, makes use of electricity. It is thus impossible that the power quality (PQ) will remain the same given that most components utilized across these processes are mostly and highly non-linear in nature. What this implies is that there will always be power quality problems, and these issues cannot be totally eliminated but can be effectively reduced. In this study, firstly, the various PQ problems were categorized accordingly and their overview given. Then, the causes and effects of these issues were succinctly listed and lastly, the ways of reducing PQ perturbations were given. Industry experts, other researchers and enthusiasts will find this study very useful.

Keywords: Power quality perturbations, Power quality problems, Domestic and commercial activities, Non-linear in nature, Power quality.

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INTRODUCTION

It is anticipated that an electrical power system will continually provide end users with appropriate sinusoidal rated current and voltage at rated frequency. The widespread use of controllers and devices based on power electronics has raised the bar for the quality of electrical power delivered to consumers. Accordingly, electrical power quality is still a major concern, particularly with the rise in sophisticated and sensitive loads connected to power networks. Given the severity of power quality issues, many electrical devices or equipment may respond negatively and noticeably. These serious issues with power quality could lead to significant equipment failure. Furthermore, it is essential for the well-being of every electrical item and gadget included in modern power networks [1-2]. Customers, equipment makers, and utilities all have rather varied ideas on what power quality (PQ) is. PQ is handled by utilities from the perspective of system reliability. While consumers view good PQ as ensuring the continuous functioning of processes, operations, and business, equipment producers see power quality as the power supply level that permits proper operation of their apparatus. Any power problem that appears as fluctuations in current, voltage, and/or frequency that cause customers' equipment to fail or malfunction is referred to as a PQ issue. Power system transients caused by switching, lightning surges, induction furnaces, and other cyclic loads were the primary source of PQ problems in the early days. Many technological and financial benefits have come from increased connectivity and the extensive utilization of power electronics gadgets with sensitive and quick management methods in electricity networks, but these developments have also presented new difficulties for power engineers [1]. Constant frequency and voltage within the specified range throughout all operations are indicative of good power quality. However, when different electrical loads are switched at random, the operational voltage and frequency fluctuate. It affects the performance of different electrical equipment as well as leads to malfunction of associated protection instruments. Conversely, low-quality electrical power results in power losses and lowers the economy and capability of the power system [2].

Voltage dip, voltage swell, voltage harmonics, current harmonics, voltage notch, flicker, undervoltage, overvoltage, DC offset, voltage unbalance, voltage fluctuations, shifts in power frequency, noise, transients (impulsive and oscillatory), interruption, and so forth are examples of PQ disturbances [2–7]. Therefore, estimating PQ parameters is crucial to reducing the negative consequences on power systems. Prior to exploring the minimization strategies of PQ perturbations (PQP), this study will first examine an overview of PQ issues and their causes.

CATEGORIZATION OF POWER QUALITY ISSUES

PQ is currently receiving increased attention as a result of its issues and the risks it poses to customers and utilities. Any type of shortcoming in the perfect sinusoidal waveforms that relate to either voltage, current, or both can be discovered in the PQ. Increased use of power electronic gadgets, which have intrinsic non-linear switching characteristics, is the primary cause of the majority of these power quality issues. Identification of PQ problems is crucial because they raise the cost of operation, maintenance, and monitoring [2, 8]. In essence, PQ perturbations (PQPs) have the potential to cause any electrical gadget to malfunction. Non-linear loads from commercial, residential, and industrial units within a power system cause deformations in current and voltage that have a detrimental effect on power system components [8]. A brief overview of notable PQ issues are herein categorized and explained.

Transients

This may be impulsive or oscillatory. A transient event is one that is unpleasant and fleeting. It is the sudden transition in steady state from one functional state to another [9]. Oscillatory transients, which can contain both negative and positive sign values, are abrupt, non-power frequency changes in the balanced state of current, voltage, or both. And are of three categories: high, medium and low frequency. Furthermore, its instantaneous value quickly shifts polarity. Conversely, an impulsive transient is a quick, unidirectional, non-power frequency changes in the balanced state of either or

both voltage and current (either positive or negative). Their decay and rise times are typically used to describe them [2, 9]. Impulsive and oscillatory transients is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Impulsive and Oscillatory Transients
Source: [10]

Short Duration Voltage Variations

Short length voltage fluctuation is defined as a deviation in the voltage's root mean square (RMS) value that lasts less than or equal to one minute. This group includes interruptions, surges, and dips (sags) [9]. A swell is characterized by an increase to between $\frac{11}{10}$ and $\frac{9}{5}$ pu in rms current or voltage at the power frequency for a period from $\frac{1}{2}$ cycle to 1 minute, whereas a sag is characterized by a reduction to between $\frac{1}{10}$ and $\frac{9}{10}$ pu at the power frequency. It suggests that sags involve brief decreases in voltage magnitude, while swells involve brief increases in voltage magnitude. When the load current or supply voltage falls to less than $\frac{1}{10}$ pu for a period of no more than one minute, this is known as a voltage interruption, or simply an interruption. Interruptions are classified as long-term or temporary and momentary. Then, momentary (lasting 0.5 cycle to 3 seconds) and temporary (lasting 3 seconds to 1 minute) interruptions fall under this category, and voltage interruptions are usually classified according to their duration [9, 10-11, 13]. Voltage dips and swells as well as interruption is shown in Figures 2 and 3 respectively.

Figure 2. Voltage Sag and Swell Events
Source: [12]

Figure 3. Voltage interruption
Source: [13]

Long Duration Voltage Variations

Long length voltage fluctuation takes place when the RMS value of the voltage varies for more than one minute. This includes prolonged disruptions that occur at both low and high voltages. When the RMS voltage drops below ninety percent of the nominal value and remains there beyond a minute, it is called an undervoltage. Conversely, an overvoltage happens when the RMS voltage increases beyond one-hundred and ten percent of the normal RMS voltage and stays there for more than a minute [9, 12]. Figure 4 shows a typical under and over voltage scenario.

Figure 4. Undervoltage and Overvoltage Events
Source: [12]

Waveform Distortion

A steady-state departure from an ideal sine wave of power frequency is known as waveform distortion. The five main forms of waveform distortion are noise, DC offset, notching, interharmonics, and harmonics. DC offset is the phrase used to describe the existence of a DC current or voltage in an alternating current power system. When current is commutated from 1 ϕ to another during the regular functioning of power electronic gadgets, a periodic voltage disturbance known as notching occurs. During notching, a brief short circuit between two different phases is typically seen. Interharmonics are currents or voltages with frequency components that are not integer multiples of the frequency (e.g., 60 or 50 Hz) at which the supply system is intended to function. Undesired electrical signals with broadband spectral content below 200 kHz that are superimposed on the power system current or voltage in phase conductors, or seen on signal lines or neutral conductors, are referred to as noise, or more precisely electrical noise. Finally, sinusoidal voltages or currents with frequencies that are integer multiples of the fundamental frequency (supply frequency) are known as harmonics. In other words, this happens when the normal current or voltage waveform is supplemented with harmonic frequencies, giving the typically smooth wave a jagged or deformed appearance [2, 9-10]. Figures 5 through 9 depict the many types of waveform distortion graphically.

Figure 5. DC offset
Source: [2]

Figure 6. Harmonics
Source: [14]

Figure 7. Noise
Source: [15]

Figure 8. Notching
Source: [16]

Figure 9. Diagram Showing Interharmonics Event
Source: [17]

Voltage Flickering

Flicker is a PQ problem where the size of the frequency or voltage change rate is perceptible to the human eye. They are seen as a continuous and rapid fluctuation of input supply voltage, maintained for a given period of time to enable visual recognition of a variation in light intensity [16]. A voltage flickering event is depicted in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Voltage Flickering
Source: [18]

Voltage Fluctuations

As seen in Figure 11, voltage variations are either a sequence of random voltage or systematic changes of the voltage envelope, with a magnitude that falls between 0.9 and 1.1 pu at frequencies

lower than 25 Hz. They are described as a sequence of intermittent or random voltage variations. Flicker is the term used to describe voltage variations induced by loads that can show constant, fast changes in the load current size. Thus, flicker is an unwanted consequence of voltage variation in some loads, whereas voltage variation itself is an electromagnetic phenomenon [2, 9].

Figure 11. Voltage Fluctuations
Source: [16]

Power Frequency Variations

The difference between the fundamental frequency of the power system and its designated nominal value (60 or 50 Hz) is known as power frequency variation [9]. This is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Frequency Variations
Source: [19]

Voltage Unbalance

The highest mismatch from the average of the 3 ϕ currents or voltages, divided by the average of the 3 ϕ currents or voltages, and given as a percentage is known as voltage unbalance, or voltage imbalance. This is seen in Figure 13 and can be stated as a fraction of the positive and negative sequence components, which in a polyphase system is often expressed as a percentage [2, 9].

Figure 13. Voltage imbalance
Source: [20]

Conclusively, the pictorial overview of all the prominent power quality problems is given in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Helicopter view of the prominent PQ issues
Source: [16]

SOURCES AND CONSEQUENCE OF POWER QUALITY ISSUES

Just having a power source is insufficient. For equipment to operate well and last a long time, the supply voltage characteristics must always be present. The power supply's quality is ascertained by its voltage features. Power quality is the extent to which the supply voltage features meet the accepted criteria. Maintaining high power quality has become essential due to the growing usage of power electronic gadgets in both residential and commercial environments, as well as sensitive equipment in automated manufacturing industries [21].

In reality, the power system deviates from its typical features due to a variety of factors, including malfunctions, fluctuating electrical consumption, and specific equipment (at the office, industry and home). Due to its direct and indirect implications, poor PQ is a major problem for end users in industrial, commercial and residential settings. For example, several household devices and appliances might not function correctly if the voltage is too low or too high, which could possibly harm the device. Electrical equipment and lightbulbs may malfunction or not work at all due to poor power quality, which ultimately results in early failure. Low PQ in industries is a concern for increasingly automated sensitive production machinery; it leads to raw material waste, equipment damage, process disruptions, output loss, and the loss of critical data. Additionally, there are numerous opportunities to lower the delivered power quality due to the complexity of a power system that carries electrical power from a location far from load centers to the point of utilization, as well as changes in demand, weather, uneven loading on the phases of distribution transformers, and consumer use of complex electronic devices, among many other factors. Essentially, poor PQ is induced by a lot of issues. PQ will deteriorate if something happens in power systems that alters the nominal values of the provided voltage, deforms the sinusoidal waveform, or compromises frequency stability [2, 21]. Table 1 shows the causes of PQ problems and the consequences that follow.

Table 1. List of PQ Issues Alongside their Sources and Effects

S/N	PQ Issue Type	Sources	Consequence
1.	Transients	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Capacitor switching in succession ✓ Energizing transformers ✓ Lightning strikes ✓ Load switching ✓ Energized lines opening and closing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ System resonance ✓ Rapid rise and fall of power signals ✓ Component failure

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ High resistance fault ✓ Opening and closing of breakers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Damage of power line insulators ✓ Hardware reboot and software glitches
2.	Voltage imbalance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 1ϕ loads on a 3ϕ circuit ✓ Blown fuses on 1ϕ of a 3ϕ capacitor bank 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Tripping of large motors ✓ Temperature rise in motors ✓ Reduction of motor efficiency
3.	Power frequency variations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Defects in the bulk power transfer system ✓ Heavy load disconnection ✓ Stoppage of heavy source of generation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ System collapse ✓ Faster or slower speed of operation of motors ✓ Equipment operation disruptions ✓ Sensitive system errors or operation failure
4.	Voltage fluctuations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Arc furnace operation ✓ Faults on distribution and transmission networks ✓ Switching of capacitive loads ✓ Brownouts ✓ Unstable generators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Affects illumination intensity of lamps ✓ Loss of system control ✓ Data loss ✓ System lock-up ✓ System shutdown ✓ Data corruption
5.	Voltage flickering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ High initial current that loads draw. E.g. elevators, arc welders and furnaces ✓ Switching ON/OFF of electric motor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Irritation to human sight ✓ Neurological problems such as headaches, epilepsy, migraine ✓ Impacts lighting for digital image capture ✓ Reduction of electronic equipment life span
6.	DC offset	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Asymmetry of converters ✓ Geomagnetic disturbance ✓ Effect of half-wave rectification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Loss of transformer life ✓ Saturated transformer core ✓ More heating ✓ Grounding electrode and other connectors electrolytic degradation
7.	Noise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Control circuits ✓ Power electronic gadgets ✓ Arcing apparatus ✓ Solid state rectifier loads 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Disturbances in sensitivity of equipment ✓ Loss of data ✓ Errors in data processing
8.	Harmonics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Fast switching of power electronic devices. E.g controlled rectifiers, inverters, uncontrolled rectifiers, cycloconverters ✓ High voltage converters. E.g high voltage drives, HVDC ✓ Other modern electronic equipment that are non-linear E.g TVs, variable speed drives, UPS, photocopying machines, printers, fluorescent lamps, computers, blenders, air conditioners, microwave ovens and so on. ✓ LED lighting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Equipment overheating ✓ Loss of machine efficiency ✓ Measurement error such as that of watt-hour and demand meters ✓ Electromagnetic interference ✓ Transformer losses such as core and eddy current losses ✓ Deterioration of motor performance ✓ Affect fuses and circuit breakers interruption capabilities
9.	Notching	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Power electronic devices ✓ Arc welding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Loss of system data ✓ Control systems mis-operation ✓ Waveform distortion ✓ Damage of capacitive components
10.	Interharmonics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Induction furnaces ✓ Cycloconverters ✓ Static frequency converters ✓ Arcing devices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Power line carrier signaling ✓ Induce visual flicker
11.	Undervoltage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Switching ON heavy loads ✓ De-energizing a capacitor bank 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Increased losses ✓ Malfunction of equipment
12.	Interruptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Lightning ✓ Insulation failure ✓ Automatic reclosure of protective gadgets ✓ Insulation flashover ✓ Transient error 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Malfunction of fire alarms ✓ Reduced production ✓ Data loss ✓ System lock-up ✓ Crash of system

		✓ ✓	Control malfunction Equipment failure	
13.	Overvoltage	✓ ✓ ✓	Energizing a capacitor bank Switching OFF heavy loads Incorrect transformer tap settings	✓ Household appliance damage ✓ Degradation of materials that provide insulation ✓ Errors in data processing ✓ Electromagnetic interference
14.	Dips	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	Inrush current Inadequate wiring Big motor starting One line-to-ground fault Energization of heavy loads System faults	✓ Loss of production ✓ Protection malfunction ✓ Malfunction of measuring and control instruments ✓ Loss of efficiency of rotating machines ✓ Loss of data ✓ Process interruption ✓ Early failure of equipment
15.	Swells	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	Source voltage variation Energizing large Capacitor banks Starting/stopping of heavy loads Poorly regulated transformer Under loading a phase and over loading other phases	✓ Apparatus damage ✓ Data loss ✓ Periodic lock-up ✓ Melting of insulating materials ✓ Excessive light glow ✓ Electromagnetic interference ✓ Too much bright screen

Source: [2, 9, 16, 21-27]

MITIGATION STRATEGIES

In order to tackle the effects induced by the various power quality issues, many solutions have been proposed by different authors. This mitigative approaches if implemented could help to curtail or eliminate the problems of poor power quality. Presented in Table 2, are the mitigative propositions of thirty scholarly works executed by various group of authors between 2019 to 2024, tailored majorly to specific PQ problems.

Table 2. Mitigative Propositions to Power Quality Problems

S/N	Reference	Year	Methodology	Strength(s)	Limitation(s)
1.	[28]	2019	Error-driven PID (proportional integral derivative) controller fine-tuned by the Grasshopper Optimization Algorithm (GOA)	Maintains load voltage stability under voltage sag, swell and imbalances; reduces harmonic distortion	Focuses on specific fault types only
2.	[29]	2020	Utilized Artificial Neural Network (ANN) controller for voltage regulation (VR)	Improved LVRT (low voltage ride through) potentiality and reduced THD (total harmonic distortion) under faults	Performance with more renewable sources was not analyzed
3.	[30]	2020	Combined ANN and Type-II Fuzzy Logic Controller (FLC) for VR	Enhanced voltage regulation and harmonic distortion control	Results may vary in larger systems with multiple disturbances
4.	[31]	2021	Utilized Self-Coupled PI (SC-PI) controller for VR	Improved disturbance rejection	Limited validation in physical systems
5.	[32]	2022	Utilized Continuous Terminal Sliding Mode Controller (CTSMC) with Self-Tuning Filter for VR	Reduced chattering effect and enhanced voltage compensation under various disturbances	THD impact was not analyzed
6.	[33]	2022	Used advanced DQ control technique with hysteresis voltage control	Effective reduction of both unbalanced and balanced voltage swells and sags	Limited scalability to larger networks

7.	[34]	2022	Used sliding-mode adaptive observer with PI controller gains optimized by moth flame optimization for VR	Effective voltage compensation under sag, swell, and phase jumps; robust response under various disturbances	Limited hardware testing
8.	[35]	2022	Utilized Flywheel Energy Storage System (FESS) with optimized Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (PMSM) for VR	Supports voltage restoration during grid interruptions and 50% sag	Designed for minimal resonance
9.	[36]	2022	Used UDE (Uncertainty and Disturbance Estimator)-based control strategy with Lyapunov stability assessment for VR	Improved robustness and harmonic rejection without frequency tuning; fast response under dynamic disturbances	Limited empirical testing in real-world grid environments
10.	[37]	2022	Used Hysteresis-band PWM (pulse width modulation) with PV (photovoltaic)-based battery storage for VR	Stabilizes power supply under various fault conditions and weather-induced disturbances	Limited THD analysis; PV-based battery storage may not be suitable for all regions
11.	[38]	2022	Utilized current-Source Inverter Interline Dynamic Voltage Restorer (CSI-IDVR) with SMES (superconducting magnetic energy storage) for VR	Low SMES capacity requirement and effective voltage stabilization	High initial cost of SMES implementation
12.	[39]	2022	SMES-based Series-Connected Compensator (SCC) with Sliding Mode Controller (SMC)	Enhanced fault handling and response accuracy	Complexity of the control structure
13.	[40]	2022	Used Second-Order Generalized Integrator (SOGI)-based Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) in each phase for VR	Mitigates power quality disturbances with fast response time	Limited scalability to three-phase systems only
14.	[41]	2022	Dynamic VR (DVR) with PI controller and Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS)	Reduces THD and voltage sags/swells within IEEE standards	Limited testing under variable load scenarios
15.	[42]	2021	Multiscale voltage variable comparisons with Boolean Signal Filters	Fast sag detection	THD assessment was not done
16.	[43]	2023	Used battery and SMES emulator for VR	Cost-effective and long-term voltage support	Full SMES systems may still outperform the hybrid setup in stability and efficiency
17.	[44]	2023	Utilized ANFIS with Hybrid Renewable Energy System (HRES) for VR	High THD reduction; addresses prolonged sags/swells	Limited hardware validation
18.	[45]	2023	Volterra adaptive expanded filter with Fractional Order PID (FOPID) for VR was used	Improved system response; reduced overshoot, undershoot, and settling time	Its computational complexity
19.	[46]	2023	Used optimal energy compensation strategy, combining pre-sag compensation and energy minimization for VR	Balanced energy efficiency and compensatory performance was achieved	Complex compensation limits analysis required for various scenarios
20.	[47]	2023	Utilized Four-leg voltage source converter with sliding mode control for VR	Enhanced stability and performance under different operating conditions	Limited real-world validation
21.	[48]	2023	Utilized DVR with PI controller optimized by Gorilla Troops Algorithm (GTA) for PQ improvement	Strong voltage regulation and harmonic rejection in high RESs (renewable energy sources) penetration scenarios	THD of source voltage and current was not measured

22.	[49]	2023	Used Recurrent Compensation Petri Fuzzy Neural Network (RCPFNN) controller for VR	Significant improvement in transient voltage quality under grid disturbances	Limited consideration of THD in source voltage and currents
23.	[50]	2023	Decentralized voltage sag mitigation through network partitioning	Voltage sag mitigation across the network was achieved	THD of source currents and voltages was not assessed
24.	[51]	2023	DVR with two-level, three-phase voltage-source converter	Rapid response (under 50 ms) to phase-wise voltage fluctuations	THD measurement of source current and voltage was not conducted
25.	[52]	2023	Application of AETI (augmented energy transformative intrinsic) algorithm with optimized filters for THD reduction	Significant THD reduction	Performance under variable load conditions was not analyzed
26.	[53]	2024	The control scheme utilizes a PD controller and an Adaptive Notch Filter optimized with IGWO (improved grey wolf optimization) algorithm	The PD controller is effective in handling frequency deviations and accelerating system response during voltage fluctuations.	The IGWO algorithm may get trapped in a local optimum, affecting the performance of the DVR.
27.	[54]	2024	Utilized an SMES-based Modular Interline DVR (MIDVR)	Compensates for voltage swells, sags, and suppresses 2nd-order voltage ripples	THD assessment was not done
28.	[55]	2024	Asymmetric Cascaded E-type Bonded T-type Multilevel Inverter (ACEBTMI) with Chattering-Free Binomial Hyperbolic SMC was employed	Precise voltage tracking and robust control for grid disturbances	High implementation cost
29.	[56]	2024	Integrated series-parallel MFIC (multi-functional integrated converter) for concurrent voltage and reactive power compensation	Enhanced equipment utilization and system reliability	Limited validation in large, variable renewable energy grids
30.	[57]	2024	DVR with adaptive fuzzy PI controller for industrial voltage stabilization	Significant voltage improvement and reduced production interruptions	Limited scalability to other industries or larger networks

Furthermore, there are several ways to guarantee high-quality power delivery in addition to the PQ mitigation techniques that several scholars have suggested. A power system's generation end, transmission end, distribution end, and end consumers' end are all possible locations for power quality problem mitigation. It should be mentioned that until certain pieces of equipment are removed, lightning strikes are avoided, or faults are fixed, the issue of PQ cannot be totally resolved. Meanwhile, the impact of PQ issues can be nearly eliminated. Mitigation strategies can assist in achieving this. Mitigation methods are crucial for reducing the effects of PQ problems. These methods seek to protect industrial processes and electrical equipment from interruptions, control voltage levels, and enhance power quality [11, 21]. A number of mitigation techniques are frequently used; this succeeding section will cover a few of them.

Voltage Regulation

In power networks, voltage regulation is essential for maintaining voltage levels within allowable bounds. Static voltage compensators (SVCs) and voltage regulators are often used devices for this purpose. These devices maintain voltage stability by compensating for variations in load demand or grid circumstances by introducing or absorbing reactive power into the system. Voltage regulation is a useful tactic for reducing voltage fluctuations before they affect downstream equipment because it provides constant control over voltage levels. Other voltage regulators include lightning arresters, transient voltage surge suppressors (TVSS), constant voltage transformers, buck-boost regulators, and tap changers [2, 11, 21].

Proper Earthing of Electrical Systems

In addition to protecting users, equipment, and installations, proper earthing of electrical systems is important for improving system performance. One factor contributing to poor power quality, especially at the end-user level, is improper earthing [21].

Uninterruptible Power Supply Systems

During voltage disruptions, uninterruptible power supply systems offer vital backup power, guaranteeing that delicate equipment continues to function. These systems defend against noise, surges, and voltage variations by using energy storage devices like flywheels or batteries to power loads during transient voltage events like sags or outages. UPS systems provide seamless power supply to vital equipment during disruptions and provide instant protection against voltage fluctuations [2, 11].

Model of Equipment

It is important for original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) to understand power quality issues and design their equipment such that it doesn't contribute to them. Equipment ought to be made less sensitive and more resilient to different types of disruptions. This will lessen the impact of power quality issues [21].

Filters

In order to prevent undesired signals from reaching the protected equipment, filters are utilized to allow the passage of desired frequencies. Capacitors, inductors, and resistors are used in the construction of filters to produce a low impedance path for the desired fundamental frequency and a high impedance path for the frequency that is meant to be eliminated. Active harmonic filters, passive harmonic filters, and hybrid harmonic filters are among the several kinds of filters. The most basic type of filter is a passive filter, which is made up of passive components like capacitors and inductors that can be tuned for a specific frequency or range of frequencies. Several passive harmonic filter topologies like LLC (inductor-inductor-capacitor), bandpass, series, LCL (inductor-capacitor-inductor), low pass, band rejection, high pass, shunt and others, have been mentioned in literature. In sensitive parts of the power system network, passive filters are used to reduce voltage bias and overpower harmonic currents. Conversely, active passive filters are made up of passive storage components like capacitors and inductors as well as power electronics interfaces. Since these filters inject actual power at the source frequency and the opposite phase to mitigate harmonic components, they are a viable substitute for traditional passive harmonic filters. Additionally, they stabilize voltage levels and eliminate harmonic currents by introducing corrective currents into the system through power electronics converters. They improve system efficiency and dependability by providing exact control over power quality factors. Hybrid harmonic filters are created by combining passive and active harmonic filters. They are said to be the best because they combine the benefits of active harmonic filters, which provide good harmonic reduction and voltage regulation, with the cost-effectiveness of passive harmonic filters. According to reports, they come in a variety of forms, including 1 ϕ , 3 ϕ three-wire, and 3 ϕ , four-wire arrangement [6, 11, 21].

Conditioners

A power line conditioner, often known as a conditioner, is a device that typically seeks to improve the PQ supplied to electrical load equipment. Active Power Conditioner (APC) and Unified Power Quality Conditioner (UPQC) are two types of conditioners. APC is thought to be one of the most effective Custom Power Devices (CPDs) that can improve system efficiency, facilitate power factor adjustment, and mitigate PQ issues like voltage dip and harmonic distortion. According to the available controller design, it is typically coupled in parallel and is thought to be a multi-function compensating device. A voltage source converter (VSC), which is the main component of an APC, transforms the DC-link voltage into 3 ϕ AC voltages with controlled amplitude, frequency, and phase. At the same time, UPQC is considered a universal active harmonic filter that combines shunt and series active harmonic filters, both of which share the same DC-link, to reduce load current and supply voltage power quality problems like neutral current, reactive current, voltage imbalance, harmonics, flickers, dips, and swells. UPQC's primary goal is to keep the supply voltage sinusoidal

at a nominal value while simultaneously preparing the source currents to become sinusoidal in phase with the source voltages. A UPQC consists of two voltage source converters in either a 1ϕ , 3ϕ three-wire, or 3ϕ four-wire arrangement that share a common DC-link. With the aid of a transformer, one of the two converters' functions as a CSI and is connected in parallel at the point of common connection (PCC), while the other converter functions as a voltage source inverter (VSI) and is connected in series between the source and the load [6].

Dynamic Voltage Restorers

Using energy storage devices and power electronics converters, dynamic voltage restorers (DVRs) are specialized devices that restore voltage within milliseconds, compensating for voltage sags and minimizing damage to sensitive equipment [11].

Availability

The grid's adequacy is determined by how well transmission lines and power plants can handle consumer energy needs and load demands. In order to meet consumer energy demands, the system must have enough infrastructure for generation, transmission, and distribution [21].

CONCLUSION

It has been established that for proper functioning of equipment and other processes tied to a given power system, the inherent power quality has to be good. As previously stated, power quality issues cannot be eliminated but rather minimized. Intentionality is thus needed for this to be achieved. It starts from ensuring that the right mechanisms are in place to forestall deterioration of the power quality. These mechanisms should be well instituted across the various components of a given power system: the generation, transmission and distribution ends precisely. As the world keeps on evolving, more complex equipment will be developed and this will add to the ongoing power quality problems faced by utilities and energy consumers. Hence, new and adaptive strategies will be needed to combat this menace. This study has assessed the different prominent PQ issues, their sources and attendant effects. And have also recommended diverse strategies of reducing these PQ problems. It is noteworthy that this recommended mitigative strategies are not exhaustive. Meaning that, there are a whole lot of other ways of effectively addressing poor power quality. Future research can thus explore this area. One of such being to comprehensively organize these mitigative strategies under a suitable framework for explicitness.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Saxena, K. S. Verma, and S. N. Singh, "Power Quality Event Classification: An Overview and Key Issues," *International Journal of Engineering, Science and Technology*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 186–199, 2010.
- [2] M. Srivastava, R. S. Shekhawat, S. K. Goyal, and G. Gangil, "A Review on Power Quality Problems, Causes and Mitigation Techniques," in *1st International Conference on Sustainable Technology for Power and Energy Systems*, 2022.
- [3] D. Mittal, O. P. Mahela, and R. Jain, "Classification of Power Quality Disturbances in Electric Power System: A Review," *IOSR Journal of Electrical and Electronics Engineering*, vol. 3, no. 5, pp. 6–14, November – December 2012.
- [4] Y. M. Esmail, A. H. K. Alaboudy, M. S. Hassan, and G. M. Dousoky, "Mitigating Power Quality Disturbances in Smart Grid using FACTS," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 1223–1235, June 2021.
- [5] Prostar (2021, Apr. 10). How to understand the Sources of Power Quality Disturbances [Online]. Available: <https://www.prostarsolar.net/article/how-to-understand-the-sources-of-power-quality-disturbances.html>

- [6] S. Choudhury and G. K. Sahoo, "A Critical Analysis of Different Power Quality Improvement Techniques in Microgrid," e-Prime - Advances in Electrical Engineering, Electronics and Energy, vol. 8, pp. 100520, March 2024.
- [7] E. Hernández-Mayoral, M. Madrigal-Martínez, J. D. Mina-Antonio, R. Iracheta-Cortez, J. A. Enríquez-Santiago, O. Rodríguez-Rivera, G. Martínez-Reyes, and E. Mendoza-Santos, "A Comprehensive Review on Power-Quality Issues, Optimization Techniques, and Control Strategies of Microgrid Based on Renewable Energy Sources," sustainability, vol. 15, pp. 9847, June 2023.
- [8] A. A. Abdelsalam, A. M. Hassanin, and H. M. Hasanien, "Categorisation of Power Quality Problems using Long Short-Term Memory Networks," IET Generation, Transmission & Distribution, vol. 15, no. 10, pp. 1626–1639, February 2021.
- [9] R. K. Jena (n.d). Electrical Power Quality [Online]. Available: https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.cet.edu.in%2Fnoticefiles%2F227_Electrical%2FPEEL5403-8th%2FSem-5%2FElectrical.pdf&psig=AOvVaw3WjI_hVGIDA0yLAAu0FaAe&ust=1745036282706000&source=image_s&cd=vfe&opi=89978449&ved=0CAcQr5oMahcKEwjgd7w3OCMAxUAAAAAHQAAAAAQBA
- [10] SRP (n.d). How SRP ensures your Power Quality [Online]. Available: <https://www.srpnet.com/customer-service/business-electric/power-quality>
- [11] M. Tyagi, M. I. Khan, and S. Gupta, "A Comprehensive Study of Voltage Swell and Sag in Power Distribution Systems: Characteristics, Causes, Effects, and Mitigation Strategies," Journal of Electrical Systems, pp. 960–972, 2024.
- [12] Testguy (2019, Nov. 23). PQ Analysis: Undervoltage, Overvoltage, Sags, Swells [Online]. Available: <https://powerquality.blog/2021/07/14/pq-analysis-undervoltage-overvoltage-sags-swells/>
- [13] Testguy (2019, Nov. 23). PQ Analysis: Power Interruptions [Online]. Available: <https://powerquality.blog/2021/07/13/pq-analysis-power-interruptions/>
- [14] IREM (2020, May 22). POWER QUALITY. Harmonics in electric Power Supply [Online]. Available: <https://www.irem.it/en/power-quality-harmonics-electric-power-supply/>
- [15] IREM (2020, Jul. 03). POWER QUALITY. High frequency disturbances [Online]. Available: <https://www.irem.it/en/power-quality-high-frequency-disturbances/>
- [16] E. Mohamed, "Power Quality Enhancement Techniques in Smart Grid," Ph.D. Thesis, Dept. Elect. Eng., Ziane Achour University of Djelfa, 2022.
- [17] M. Mao, X. Ni, Z. Xu, H. Sun, and C. Yin, "A Comprehensive Analysis of the Influencing Factors of Interharmonics on a Distributed PV Grid-Connected Power Generation System," energies, vol. 17, pp. 5958, November 2024.
- [18] Dewetron (2022, Mar. 11). Flicker in Electrical Systems [Online]. Available: <https://www.dewetron.com/news/flicker-in-electrical-systems/>
- [19] M. S. Priyadarshini, M. Bajaj, L. Prokop, and M. Berhanu, "Perception of Power Quality Disturbances using Fourier, Short-Time Fourier, Continuous and Discrete Wavelet Transforms," scientific reports, vol. 14, pp. 3443, 2024.
- [20] EM Magazine (2025, Apr. 18). The importance of not losing your balance! [Online]. Available: <https://www.energymanagermagazine.co.uk/the-importance-of-not-losing-your-balance/>
- [21] D. O. Johnson and K. A. Hassan, "Issues of Power Quality in Electrical Systems," International Journal of Energy and Power Engineering, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 148–154, July 2016.
- [22] V. Anand and S. K. Srivastava, "Causes, Effects and Solutions of Poor Quality Problems in the Power Systems," Vikash Anand et al Int. Journal of Engineering Research and Applications, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 67–74, May 2014.
- [23] M. Azeem (2024, Nov. 01). Understanding Harmonics and Power Quality in Electrical Systems [Online]. Available: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/understanding-harmonics-power-quality-electrical-muhammad-4ucmf>

- [24] Helios Power Solutions (n.d). AC Power Quality Problems [Online]. Available: <https://heliosps.com/knowledgebase/ac-power-quality-problems-solutions/>
- [25] G. Singh, "Electric Power Quality-Issues, Effects and Mitigation," *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology*, vol. 2, no. 6, pp. 933–944, June 2013.
- [26] P. Esteban (2021, Mar. 11). Power quality problems and advanced power electronics solutions [Online]. Available: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/power-quality-problems-advanced-electronics-solutions-pedro-esteban-5c>
- [27] withthegrid (2024, Nov. 06). Intro to Power Quality: The Overlooked Challenge of the Energy Transition [Online]. Available: <https://withthegrid.com/introduction-to-power-quality/>
- [28] A. I. Omar, S. H. E. Abdel Aleem, E. E. A. El-Zahab, M. Algablawy, and Z. M. Ali, "An Improved Approach for Robust Control of Dynamic Voltage Restorer and Power Quality Enhancement using Grasshopper Optimization Algorithm," *ISA Transactions*, vol. 95, pp. 110–129, 2019.
- [29] W. S. Hassanein, M. M. Ahmed, M. O. A. El-Raouf, M. G. Ashmawy, and M. I. Mosaad, "Performance Improvement of Off-Grid Hybrid Renewable Energy System using Dynamic Voltage Restorer," *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, vol. 59, no. 3, pp. 1567–1581, 2020.
- [30] N. Mallick and V. Mukherjee, "Maximum Power Point Tracking Supported Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell Based Intelligent Dynamic Voltage Restorer," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 45, no. 53, pp. 29271–29287, 2020.
- [31] J. Ma, J. Bai, and W. Wang, "Research on Dynamic Voltage Restorer Based on Self-Coupled Proportional–Integral Controller," *Energy Reports*, vol. 7, pp. 150–160, 2021.
- [32] H. Ahmed, S. Biricik, H. Komurcugil, S. B. Elghali, and M. Benbouzid, "Enhanced Frequency-Adaptive Self-Tuning Filter-Based Continuous Terminal Sliding Mode Control of Single-Phase Dynamic Voltage Restorer," *Control Engineering Practice*, vol. 128, pp. 105340, 2022.
- [33] S. F. Al-Gahtani, A. B. Barnawi, H. Z. Azazi, S. M. Irshad, J. K. Bhutto, H. M. Majahar, and E. Z. M. Salem, "A New Technique Implemented in Synchronous Reference Frame for DVR Control Under Severe Sag and Swell Conditions," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 25565–25579, 2022.
- [34] S. R. Arya, R. Maurya, T. A. Naidu, and B. C. Babu, "Adaptive Observer for Dynamic Voltage Restorer with Optimized Proportional Integral Gains," *Chinese Journal of Electrical Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 38–52, 2022.
- [35] O. Aydogmus, G. Boztas, and R. Celikel, "Design and Analysis of a Flywheel Energy Storage System Fed by Matrix Converter as a Dynamic Voltage Restorer," *Energy*, vol. 238, pp. 121687, 2022.
- [36] S. DaneshvarDehnavi, C. Negri, S. Bayne, and M. Giesselmann, "Dynamic Voltage Restorer (DVR) with a Novel Robust Control Strategy," *ISA Transactions*, vol. 121, pp. 316–326, 2022.
- [37] A. Farooqi, M. M. Othman, M. A. M. Radzi, I. Musirin, S. Z. M. Noor, and I. Z. Abidin, "Dynamic Voltage Restorer (DVR) Enhancement in Power Quality Mitigation with an Adverse Impact of Unsymmetrical Faults," *Energy Reports*, vol. 8, pp. 871–882, 2022.
- [38] J. X. Jin, Q. Zhou, R. H. Yang, Y. J. Li, H. Li, Y. G. Guo, and J. G. Zhu, "A Superconducting Magnetic Energy Storage Based Current-Type Interline Dynamic Voltage Restorer for Transient Power Quality Enhancement of Composited Data Center and Renewable Energy Source Power System," *Journal of Energy Storage*, vol. 52, pp. 105003, 2022.
- [39] Y. Li, J. Jin, and L. Wang, "A Dual-Function SMES-Based Series-Connected Compensator of Dynamic Voltage Restoration and Fault Current Limitation for Photovoltaic Microgrid," *Energy Reports*, vol. 8, pp. 312–320, 2022.
- [40] R. Nasrollahi, H. F. Farahani, M. Asadi, and M. Farhadi-Kangarlu, "Sliding Mode Control of a Dynamic Voltage Restorer Based on PWM AC Chopper in Three-Phase Three-Wire Systems," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 134, pp. 107480, 2022.

- [41] D. Prasad and C. Dhanamjayulu, "Solar PV Integrated Dynamic Voltage Restorer for Enhancing the Power Quality Under Distorted Grid Conditions," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 213, pp. 108746, 2022.
- [42] H. Zhang, G. Xiao, Z. Lu, and Y. Chai, "Reduce Response Time of Single-Phase Dynamic Voltage Restorer (DVR) in a Wide Range of Operating Conditions for Practical Application," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 2101–2113, 2021.
- [43] M. S. Adhve and B. N. Chaudhari, "Optimizing Dynamic Voltage Restoration: A Hybrid Approach with SMES Emulator and Battery Storage," in *2023 IEEE Fifth International Conference on Advances in Electronics, Computers and Communications*, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [44] A. A. Ben, Y. Mouloudi, and M. A. Soumeur, "Integration of Renewable Energy Sources in the Dynamic Voltage Restorer for Improving Power Quality Using ANFIS Controller," *Journal of King Saud University - Engineering Sciences*, vol. 35, no. 8, pp. 539–548, 2023.
- [45] P. Kumar and S. R. Arya, "Performance Evaluation of Dynamic Voltage Restorer Using Intelligent Control Algorithm," *E-Prime - Advances in Electrical Engineering, Electronics and Energy*, vol. 6, pp. 100382, 2023.
- [46] S. Li, X. Chang, H. Wang, N. Liu, Y. Liu, Y. Yang, and Q. Duan, "Dynamic Voltage Restorer Based on Integrated Energy Optimal Compensation," *Electronics*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 531, 2023.
- [47] L. Nalla, M. K. Mishra, and A. Ghosh, "Sliding Mode Control of a Four-Leg Dynamic Voltage Restorer in a Natural Reference Frame," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Industrial Electronics*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 919–927, 2023.
- [48] M. Rawa, H. N. Mohamed, Y. Al-Turki, K. Sedraoui, and A. M. Ibrahim, "Dynamic Voltage Restorer Under Different Grid Operating Conditions for Power Quality Enhancement with the Deployment of a PI Controller Using Gorilla Troops Algorithm," *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, vol. 14, no. 10, pp. 102172, 2023.
- [49] K. H. Tan, J. H. Chen, and Y. D. Lee, "Intelligent Controlled Dynamic Voltage Restorer for Improving Transient Voltage Quality," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 74686–74701, 2023.
- [50] H. Tarimoradi, S. Mahmoodi, and N. Rezaei, "Network Leveling Based on Voltage-Sag Mitigation Using Dynamic Voltage Restorers," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 220, pp. 109348, 2023.
- [51] V. Torres-García, G. Castillo-García, G. Mejía-Ruiz, and M. R. Arrieta-Paternina, "Dynamic Voltage Restorer Controlled Per Independent Phases for Power Quality Sags-Swells Mitigation Under Unbalanced Conditions," in *Monitoring and Control of Electrical Power Systems Using Machine Learning Techniques*, Elsevier, 2023, pp. 245–261.
- [52] G. Venugopal, A. K. Udayakumar, N. Saha, A. N. Kalavathy, A. Balashanmugham, and B. Vasudevan, "Augmented Energy Transformative Intrinsic Algorithm Based Improved Power Quality in Fuel Cell Driven Dynamic Voltage Restorer," *Computers and Electrical Engineering*, vol. 111, part A, pp. 108952, 2023.
- [53] M. M. Alrashed, A. Flah, M. Dashtdar, C. Z. El-Bayeh, and M. F. Elnaggar, "Improving the Control Strategy of the DVR Compensator Based on an Adaptive Notch Filter with an Optimized PD Controller Using the IGWO Algorithm," *International Transactions on Electrical Energy Systems*, 2024.
- [54] X. Xiao, M. Zhang, R. Yang, X. Chen, and Z. Zheng, "Superconducting Magnetic Energy Storage Based Modular Interline Dynamic Voltage Restorer for Renewable-Based MTDC Network," *Applied Energy*, vol. 371, pp. 123629, 2024.
- [55] A. F. Darvish, "Novel Chattering Free Binomial Hyperbolic Sliding Mode Controller for Asymmetric Cascaded E-Type Bonded T-Type Multilevel Inverter-Based Dynamic Voltage Restorer to Meliorate FRT Capability of DFIG-Based Wind Turbine," *Results in Engineering*, vol. 23, pp. 102370, 2024.

[56] Q. Guo, Y. Hou, C. Tu, Z. Huang, F. Jiang, Z. Xu, L. Wang, and F. Xiao, "A Multi-functional Integrated Converter for Dynamic Voltage Restoration and Reactive Power Compensation in Active Distribution Networks," IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy, pp. 1–12, 2024.

[57] B. Molla, E. M. Molla, A. W. Yimam, and T. M. Azerefegn, "Mitigation of Ethiopian Industry Sector Power Quality Problems Using Ultra-Capacitor Based Dynamic Voltage Restorer," E-Prime - Advances in Electrical Engineering, Electronics and Energy, vol. 8, pp. 100612, 2024.

